

Mass transport impedance in a proton-exchange membrane fuel cell under passive operation conditions

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Highlights

- Transport impedance with Current-modulated Hydrogen flow-rate Spectroscopy (CH2S).
- Effective diffusivities and mass transport resistances of hydrogen measured with CH2S.
- GDL substrate and MPL layers operando transport properties differentiated.
- Transport properties compared for passive-PEMFC and conventional-PEMFC
- Current density and active area effects on hydrogen transport in passive PEMFC.

Graphical abstract

Passive PEMFC: hydrogen and water transport

CH2S: anodic hydrogen transport impedance

DRT analysis of CH2S

Abstract

Current-modulated Hydrogen flow-rate Spectroscopy (CH2S) is the mass-transport impedance that relates cell current (\tilde{I}) and hydrogen flow rate (\tilde{Q}_{H_2}) in the anode of a proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC). The transfer function ($H = nF\tilde{Q}_{H_2}/\tilde{I}$) provides kinetic information about transport processes in the anode of a PEMFC under working conditions. CH2S can differentiate hydrogen transport in the gas diffusion layer substrate (GDLS) and in the microporous layer (MPL) of the anode. Using an analytical model and the distribution of relaxation times formalism, the effective, *operando*, hydrogen diffusivities and mass transport resistances of the GDLS and MPL are obtained. Here CH2S is used to study mass transport in a PEMFC anode fed with quasi-static hydrogen and air atmospheres, or passive PEMFC (p-PEMFC). The anode is a commercial gas diffusion electrode, with Pt/C based catalyst layer, a hydrophobic carbon black MPL, and a woven carbon cloth GDLS. The results show larger mass transport losses in the GDLS of the p-PEMFC compared with a convective PEMFC (c-PEMFC) fed with gases under forced convection. The MPL, however, presents same mass transport losses in both cell types, with *operando* water saturation close to 100%. Increasing current density, up to 180 mA cm⁻², has little impact on GDLS transport properties but improves them in the MPL attributed to thermal activation and drier conditions in the anode by water electroosmotic dragging. Larger active area size increases transport losses in p-PEMFC due to more difficult passive elimination of water from the cell by natural forces. Changes in the p-PEMFC design are proposed to mitigate mass transport losses and bring its efficiency closer to the c-PEMFC.

Keywords: PEMFC, transport Impedance, anode, passive cell, distribution of relaxation time (drt)

1. Introduction

Mass transport impedances are techniques of interest to study transport processes in electrochemical cells without interference from electrochemical charge transfer kinetics [1,2]. They are especially useful for the study of cells with gaseous reactants, like proton-exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) [3–7]. Among them, the *Current-modulated Hydrogen-flow rate Spectroscopy* (CH2S) relates the perturbed hydrogen flow rate at the anode inlet, \tilde{Q}_{H_2} , with the current perturbation, \tilde{I} . The CH2S transfer function, $\mathbf{H}(j\omega)$, obeys the following relation [8,9]:

$$\mathbf{H}(j\omega) = nF \frac{\tilde{Q}_{H_2}}{\tilde{I}}, \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of exchanged electrons ($n=2$ for hydrogen oxidation), F ($=96485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$) the Faraday constant, ω the angular frequency, and j is the complex number. Solving the transport equation for the gas diffusion layer (GDL) of the anode, an analytical expression is obtained for the transfer function [9]:

$$\mathbf{H}(j\omega) = \operatorname{sech} \left(L_{GDL} \sqrt{\frac{j\omega}{D_{eff}}} \right), \quad (2)$$

where L_{GDL} is the GDL thickness, and D_{eff} is the *operando*, effective hydrogen diffusivity. CH2S experimental curves normally show multiple time constants due to mass-transport resistances in different components of the electrode. Hence, the GDL contributes with losses from the substrate (GDLS) and the microporous layer (MPL), while other transport resistances may appear, like the inlet port, the flow-field channel, and the catalyst layer (CL) [8,10]. For cases with multiple mass transport losses, a serial combination of impedances can be used to fit the experimental curves [9]:

$$\mathbf{H}(j\omega) = \sum_i \left[w_i \operatorname{sech} \left(L_i \sqrt{\frac{j\omega}{D_{eff,i}}} \right) \right], \quad (3)$$

where w_i is the weight factor of the i transport resistance. Faraday law, which is implicit in the transfer function expression (Eq.1), requires:

$$\sum_i w_i = 1, \quad (4)$$

which is accomplished when CH2S measurements are carried out under full dead-end anode conditions, i.e. with stoichiometric factor $\lambda_{H_2} = 1$. Deviations from Eq.4 may indicate the presence of hydrogen chemical kinetics in the GDL ($\sum_i w_i < 1$), or the existence of hydrogen losses by non-faradaic processes like cross-over or leakage ($\sum_i w_i > 1$) [9].

Passive operation of a PEMFC consists of feeding the cell without applying convection to gases inlet [11–20]. Such operation mode avoids some external auxiliaries and their parasitic power consumption, which makes lighter and more efficient hydrogen power systems, suitable for application in small and portable electric devices [21]. Steady and high power production in passive PEMFCs (p-PEMFCs) poses important challenges because the transport of liquid water in the electrodes and its elimination from the cell is passive, or exclusively driven by chemical potentials [22]. Fig. 1 shows the principal water transport processes acting inside the porous cathode layers (Fig. 1a) and on its surface (Fig. 1b) in a p-PEMFC during power production.

Fig. 1 Liquid water transport in the cathode of a p-PEMFC, a) inside the porous electrode by surface diffusion (1), capillary transport (2), and droplet percolation (3); and b) over the cathode surface in contact with a columnar plate, by

evaporation (4), interaction with the columns plate (5), interactions among droplets (6), and gravity dragging (7). Back-diffusion and electro-osmotic drag transport through the membrane are also indicated.

Passive transport of liquid water comprises principally surface diffusion (1), capillarity (2), and droplet percolation (3) inside the CL, MPL, and GDLS, while evaporation (4), interaction with the cathodic plate (5), droplets hydrophilic interactions (6), and gravity dragging (7) actuate on water drops emerging at the electrode surface. In the anode, water saturation and hydrogen transport conditions are closely related to the situation in the cathode side due to the fast water exchange through the hydrophilic membrane by means of electroosmotic dragging and back diffusion (Fig. 1b). Water management is for this reason a key process for gas transport in both electrodes of a PEMFC, and has been studied by different methods, like optical [23], electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) [24–26], water collection experiments [27,28], X-ray radiography [29–32], and neutron radiography [33], and modelled using Lattice Boltzmann [34–36] and pore network methods [37]. Satjaritanun *et al.* [38], combining simulation and X-ray computed tomography have studied water dynamics in GDLS and MPL in dependence of microstructure and wetting properties. They found that liquid water generated in the cathodic CL spreads all over the MPL before it moves towards the GDLS, with transport characterized by two capillary pressures, one for droplets breakthrough and the other for steady-state flow. Salaberri *et al.* [36] computed the effective diffusivity of partially wetted GDLS and obtained power laws of the type $(1-s_{avg})^n$ as a function of the average saturation (s_{avg}) with exponent $n = 3$ for through plane and $n = 2$ for in-plane diffusive transport. While water transport inside the porous electrodes follows essentially the same physical processes in p-PEMFC and conventional-convective PEMFC (c-PEMFC), the removal of droplets from the cathode's back surface is essentially different. In the c-PEMFC, droplets adhesion is overcome by the convective flow of gas within the flow-field channels leading to rapid removal rates and low GDL water saturation, typically below 25% [39,40]. Das *et al.* [40] measured the adhesion forces on the GDL surface and showed a dependency on creation method and history. In p-PEMFC, droplets are removed by passive forces, of the type shown in Fig. 1b, which are dependent on ambient conditions and cell orientation [41,42]. The

action of passive forces on the cathode surface can be favored with special cathodic plate designs, like the columnar plate [43] that maximizes ambient air contact with the cathode back surface, allows mobility of water drops, and the effect of natural warm air streams upwards [19,44,45]. The passive elimination of water governs the saturation state of porous gas diffusion electrodes and limits the transport of air and hydrogen inside a p-PEMFC.

CH2S distinguishes *operando* effective diffusivities among different porous phases of the anode, like GDLS and MPL [8–10,46]. Such property is unique among methods used to study transport properties in PEMFCs. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), for instance, is sensitive to transport in the cathode as a whole, and assuming unmodulated anode reference electrode [24,25,47,48]. Limiting current techniques can provide transport properties of both PEMFC electrodes, *in-situ* and *operando*, using oxygen concentration limitation or hydrogen pump configuration, respectively [49]. Although all these techniques are sensitive to transport properties of porous media, however assumptions and measuring conditions are different, therefore results may also differ as discussed in Section 3 (Results and Discussion).

In this work, CH2S technique is used for the study of hydrogen transport properties in a p-PEMFC. *Operando* diffusivity of hydrogen and the transport resistance are measured in a p-PEMFC and compared with those of a c-PEMFC. The effects of current density and active area size on p-PEMFC transport properties are also studied. Results show the important differences existing in transport properties in both cell configurations, and between the MPL and the GDLS.

2. Experimental part

The p-PEMFC design has been described in previous works [43] (see also Fig. 1S in Supplementary Information). The cell has circular active area (diameters used here are 30 mm and 40 mm), with air-breathing cathode and dead-end anode. The cathode gas diffusion electrode (GDE) is commercial (FCSTORE), with 0.30 mg Pt·cm⁻² catalyst loading (Pt on Vulcan), 30 wt% ionomer in CL, and

10 μm CL thickness; the GDL (W1S1011) is a woven carbon fiber cloth substrate (GDLS) with 5 wt% PTFE treatment, covered by a hydrophobic MPL ($> 130^\circ$ water contact angle). A cross-sectional SEM image of the GDE is shown in Fig. 3S of the Supplementary Information. In the p-PEMFC, the GDE cathode back surface is in contact with a gold-coated Ni-grid (Dexmet) as current collector, and an aluminum cathodic plate with columnar design [43], fasten with four bolts (M3) at a calibrated torque (0.3 Nm). Same commercial GDE and grid collector are used in the anode, which is placed in a gastight chamber. The electrolyte membrane is Nafion 212NR (Ion Power Inc.). Operation of the p-PEMFC is carried out with cathode in contact with ambient air (23 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 30%RH), while the anode chamber is fed with a dry and static H_2 atmosphere at 0.8 bar_g (Air Liquide, 99.999%). Steady-state polarization curves are obtained by constant current steps and 200 s dwell time while the cell is self-heated attaining a temperature of 35 $^\circ\text{C} \pm 5$ $^\circ\text{C}$.

A conventional single PEMFC (c-PEMFC), fed with air and H_2 streams, of 15.2 cm^2 square active area, was also tested, with same GDEs and membrane as the p-PEMFC. The c-PEMFC has gold coated stainless steel 316 (3mm thickness) flow field plates with double serpentine channels of 1mm² cross section area each, in cross-flow disposition anode vs. cathode. Steady-state polarization curves were measured under H_2/Air , $\lambda_{\text{H}_2} = 1.5/\lambda_{\text{O}_2} = 3.0$, at 40 $^\circ\text{C}$, and atmospheric pressure. As for the p-PEMFC the curve was taken under constant load steps with 200 s dwell time.

CH₂S measurements were carried out under galvanostatic conditions (Kikusui PLZ164WA), by superposing $I_{p-p} = 50$ mA current modulation with the frequency generator of a potentiostat (Autolab 30N, Metrohm). The hydrogen flow-rate was measured with an electronic flow-meter (AWM3100V, Honeywell) placed before the anode inlet port. The flow-meter was calibrated with a bubble flow-meter and with the p-PEMFC itself, using Faraday equation, finding reasonable good agreement between both methods. The frequency response analyser of the potentiostat was used to obtain the CH₂S transfer function by connecting the flow-meter output signal to the X-port, and the current load output signal to the Y-port. More details of the CH₂S set-up can be found in [10]. Measurements were

carried out in the frequency range from 1 kHz to 0.01 Hz. For the analysis of CH₂S results, and calculation of the hydrogen effective diffusivities and mass transport resistances, Eq. 3 was implemented in a commercial analytic software (Origin Pro 2022). A scheme of the experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 2S of the Supplementary Material together with photographs of the c- and p-PEMFCs.

As a complementary analysis of CH₂S results, the distribution of relaxation times (DRT) method was used. DRT is based on the representation of the impedance as an infinite series of parallel resistor-capacitor elements (Voigt elements) [50]. A function is obtained, $g(\tau)$ (Ohm s⁻¹), that corresponds to the resistance weight at each characteristic time. The relation between the impedance and the DRT function ($\gamma(\ln \tau) = \tau g(\tau)$) is:

$$Z(\omega_i) = R_0 + Z_{pol}(\omega_i) = R_0 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\gamma(\ln \tau)}{1 + \omega_i \tau} d \ln \tau, \quad (5)$$

where $Z(\omega_i)$ is the impedance at the angular frequency ω_i , R_0 is the ohmic resistor, and $\gamma(\ln \tau) d \ln \tau$ is the resistance of kinetic processes with time constants between $\ln \tau$ and $\ln \tau + d \ln \tau$. A plot $\gamma(\ln \tau)$ vs. $\ln \tau$ shows peaks of single relaxation processes at their characteristic time, with area of the peak proportional to the resistance. By this means, DRT analysis shows dynamic processes present in the impedance data without any previous knowledge of the system under study. Impedance data must accomplish the linear, time-invariance, and causal relationships, as verified by a Kramers-Kronig test [51–53]. DRT has been used to analyze the electrochemical impedance ($Z(\omega) = \tilde{V}/\tilde{I}$) of PEMFCs [54–56] and electrolyzers [57], as well as for other impedance types, like the intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopy [58–60], and thermal impedance spectroscopy [61]. Here, DRT is applied to the analysis of CH₂S to help in the identification of single mass transport processes in the anode, hence:

$$Z_{CH_2S}(\omega_i) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\gamma_{CH_2S}(\ln \tau)}{1 + \omega_i \tau} d \ln \tau. \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma_{CH2S}(\ln \tau)$ is adimensional (c.f. Eq. 1). Compared to Eq.5, there is no pure resistive term in Eq. 6, which means that there is no mass transport resistance at sufficiently high current modulation frequency (mass transport resistance always coexists with a mass storage capacity). DRTtools web platform [50,62] was used to calculate $\gamma_{CH2S}(\ln \tau)$ using the Gaussian radial basis discretization function with FWHM coefficient 0.5, and 1st order regularization derivative using $\lambda = 0.001$ regularization parameter. Discretization of $\gamma(\ln \tau)$ followed by regularized regression are necessary steps to invert and solve Eq. 6 [50].

3. Results and discussion

Hydrogen transport in the anode of a PEMFC is very sensitive to cell operation parameters. In dead-end mode, the transport is challenged by liquid water accumulation in the cell, as reflected by the CH2S results in Fig. 2 comparing a p-PEMFC with a c-PEMFC.

Fig. 2. a) CH2S and b) DRT analysis, of a p-PEMFC (black) and a c-PEMFC (red). The lines in a) correspond to the fitting to Eq. 3, with results given in Table II. Cell current $i = 100 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, cell temperature $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The DRT functions of Fig. 2b show characteristic peaks that help to identify different transport processes in the dead-end anodes. The assignments are summarized in Table I, based on the analysis of CH2S results carried out in previous studies [8,9].

Table I. Assignment of CH₂S peaks in Fig.2b.

Signal	Assignment	Characteristic Time
#1	Experimental high frequency limit	< 0.003 s
#1b	Flow-field plate of the c-PEMFC	0.003 < τ < 0.01
#2	Anodic GDLS	0.01 < τ < 5
#3	Anodic MPL	0.5 < τ < 100

The high frequency peak #1 is the experimental time response limitation, which is principally due to the flow-rate meter [10], although it has some dependence on characteristics of the cell as it is shown below. A second high frequency peak #1b, only observed in c-PEMFC, is assigned to hydrogen transport impedance in the inlet and flow-field of this cell. This peak will not be analyzed in this work. Peaks #2 and #3 appearing at longer times are due to mass transport limitations in the anodic GDE. In the range 0.1 s < τ < 1 s, peak #2 is assigned to the GDLS, which in this work is a commercial woven carbon cloth with. Peak #3 at the lowest frequencies, 0.5 s < τ < 100 s, is attributed to the MPL, a hydrophobic carbon black film. A cross-sectional SEM image of the GDE is shown in the Supplementary Material, Fig. 3S. Other transport processes in the anode, not appearing in the results presented here, are the hydrogen cross-over through the electrolyte membrane (Nafion 212NR, 50 μ m), and hydrogen leakage, that give rise to $|H| > 1$ in CH₂S spectra. Hydrogen transport impedance in the anodic CL is so far, not distinguished in CH₂S spectra.

Operando transport parameters of the anodic layers have been determined by fitting CH₂S results to Eq. 3 (Fig. 2a). The most characteristic parameter is the effective diffusivity that depends on structural properties of the porous media and saturation state [36]:

$$D_{eff,i} = D_{bulk} \frac{\epsilon_i}{\tau_i} (1 - s_{avg})^n, \quad (7)$$

where D_{bulk} is the bulk and dry molecular diffusion coefficient, ϵ_i the porosity, τ_i the tortuosity, s_{avg} the average saturation, with n as phenomenological exponent. For each signal, a characteristic time, k_i , is obtained from which $D_{eff,i}$ can be

calculated using Eq. 8. Another transport related parameter of interest is the mass transport resistance of the layer, $R_{mt,i}$, corresponding to the hydrogen concentration gradient per unit current density ($R_{mt} = nF \Delta C/i$), as calculated from Eq. 9:

$$D_{eff,i} = \frac{L_i^2}{k_i} \quad (8)$$

$$R_{mt,i} = \frac{k_i}{L_i} \quad (9)$$

For calculations the thicknesses measured from SEM cross sectional images after cell compression was be used, namely $L_{GDLS} = 215 \mu\text{m} \pm 30 \mu\text{m}$, and $L_{MPL} = 83 \mu\text{m} \pm 30 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 3S), with standard deviation due to heterogeneities inherent in the carbon cloth GDLS, and MPL coating with non-uniform penetration into the GDLS. The resulting *operando* effective diffusivities and mass transport resistances of hydrogen are in Table II for the GDLS and MPL of a p-PEMFC and a c-PEMFC.

Table II. Results of the fitting of the CH2S results in Fig. 2a to the theory (Eq. 3) and signal assignation according to Table I, for the passive (p-PEMFC) and the convective (c-PEMFC) cell. Effective hydrogen diffusivities and mass transport resistances calculated from Eqs. 8 and 9, respectively.

Signal	Assignment	Parameter	p-PEMFC	c-PEMFC
#1	Experimental	w_1	0.813±0.008	0.75±0.06
		k_1, s	0.0038±0.0001	0.0025±0.0003
#2	Anodic GDLS	w_2	0.06±0.04	0.19±0.06
		k_2, s	1.3±0.9	0.019±0.009
		$D_{eff,GDLS}, cm^2 s^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$	0.36±0.25	24±11
		$R_{mt,GDLS}, s cm^{-1}$	60±40	0.88±0.42
#3	Anodic MPL	w_3	0.13±0.03	0.07±0.04
		k_3, s	8±3	5±4
		$D_{eff,MPL}, cm^2 s^{-1} \times 10^{-5}$	0.86±0.3	1.4±1.1
		$R_{mt,MPL}, s cm^{-1}$	960±360	600±480

The differences in diffusivities from p- to c-PEMFC must be attributed to the different operation conditions. Hence, in p-PEMFC the GDLS registers an important decrease compared with the c-PEMFC ($D_{eff,GDLS} = 0.36 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ vs. $24 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) that reflects higher water saturation under passive operation [63]. In contrast, signal #3, shows similar diffusivity in MPLs of both cells, with differences within the experimental error, $D_{eff,GDLS} = 0.86 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1.4 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for p-PEMFC and c-PEMFC, respectively. More comments on the diffusivities obtained for GDLS and MPL, and compared those obtained with other techniques, can be found at the end of this section.

Current density. CH2S results at four current densities, from 10 mA cm^{-2} to 180 mA cm^{-2} , are shown in Fig. 3 for the p-PEMFC cell, with results of the analysis of the signals in Table III. Current density increases liquid water saturation inside the electrodes and the temperature of the cell (temperatures measured on the cathodic plate of the self-heated p-PEMFC are in Table III). The results of the analysis show that GDLS parameters remain constant in the current density range probed here, indicating little change in hydrogen transport conditions in this layer. However, MPL diffusivity improves notably with current density.

Fig. 3. a) DRT analysis, and b) CH2S of a p-PEMFCs (30 mm active area diameter), at four different current densities. Lines in a) correspond to the fitting to Eq. 3, with results in Table III.

Table III. Results of the fitting of the CH₂S in Fig. 3 to the theory (Eq. 3), for a p-PEMFC cell run at different current densities. Effective diffusivities and mass transport resistances are plotted in Fig. 4.

Current:			$i = 10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$	$i = 40 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$	$i = 110 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$	$i = 180 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$
Temperature:			30.6 °C	34.8 °C	39.8 °C	41.1 °C
Signal	Assign.	Parameter				
#1	Exp.	w_1	0.958±0.007	0.894±0.005	0.883±0.005	0.877±0.005
		$k_1, \text{ s}$	0.0033±0.00007	0.0031±0.00005	0.0030±0.00005	0.0029±0.00004
#2	GDLS	w_2	0.069±0.01	0.063±0.01	0.045±0.011	0.043±0.015
		$k_2, \text{ s}$	0.47±0.14	0.43±0.12	0.42±0.17	0.50±0.26
		$D_{eff,GDLS}$	see Fig. 4b			
		$R_{mt,GDLS}$				
#3	MPL	w_3	0.09±0.01	0.09±0.01	0.09±0.01	0.09±0.01
		$k_3, \text{ s}$	15±4	8±2	4.6±1	4±1
		$D_{eff,MPL}$	see Fig. 4a			
		$R_{mt,MPL}$				

The effective diffusivities and mass transport are plotted in Figs. 4a and b as a function of current density, and compared with those of a c-PEMFC measured under similar conditions. Lower hydrogen diffusivity in the anodic GDLS of the p-PEMFC reflects higher water contents in this cell type (see also Fig.2), while both cells show little dependence of this parameter on current density (Fig. 4a). The increase in diffusivity in the MPL with current density is similar for p-PEMFC and c-PEMFC (Fig. 4b), also observed in previous work [9], and must be attributed to the thermal activation of mass transport (see cell temperatures in Table III) together with drier conditions in the anode by removal of water by electroosmotic drag. Both effects contribute to hydrogen transport improvement in the anodic MPL under passive and convective PEMFC operation.

Fig. 4. GDLS (a) and MPL (b) hydrogen mass transport resistances (continuous lines), and effective diffusivities (dashed lines), as a function of current density, for the anodes of p-PEMFC (black lines) and c-PEMFC (red lines). The p-PEMFC was operated under ambient air conditions (23°C, 35%RH) and dead-end anode (dry hydrogen 1 barg). The c-PEMFC was operated at 30°C, with H₂/O₂, dead-end anode, and stoichiometry in cathode $\lambda = 3.0$, 1barg, and 100% RH.

Steady-state polarization curves of p- and c-PEMFC are presented in Fig. 5. Identical response is observed at low current density, < 150 mA·cm⁻², while a clear differentiation is observed above between both cell types (c-PEMFC was operated at 40 °C and ambient pressure to compare with p-PEMFC conditions). The differences due to active area size of p-PEMFC shown in this figure are commented below.

Fig. 5. Steady-state polarization curves (a) and power density (b) of two p-PEMFCs with 7.1 cm² and 12.6 cm² circular active areas, respectively, under operation conditions as in Fig. 4. Also included the curves of a c-PEMFC operated at 40°C, H₂/air at 1.5/3.0 stoichiometries, 100% RH, and atmospheric pressure (taken from Fig. 4, reference [43]).

Active area size. Increasing the active area of a p-PEMFC is of technical interest to improve the power density of passive hydrogen systems. However, as shown in the polarization curves of Fig. 5, increasing the area from 7.1 cm² to 12.6 cm² leads to an important decay in the intermediate-high current density range and in the peak power density. The effect on mass transport properties can be inferred from CH₂S in Fig. 6 and their analysis in Table IV.

Fig. 6. a) DRT analysis, and b) CH₂S of two p-PEMFCs with 40mm and 30mm active area diameter. The lines in b) correspond to the fitting to Eq. 3, with results in Table IV. Measurements taken at $i = 100 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and 35 °C cell temperature.

Table IV. Results of the fitting of the CH₂S in Fig. 6 to the theory (Eq. 3), for two passive cells with different active area size (A_{act}).

Signal	Assignment	Parameter	$A_{act} = 7.1 \text{ cm}^2$	$A_{act} = 12.6 \text{ cm}^2$
#1	Experimental	w_1	0.855 ± 0.004	0.828 ± 0.007
		$k_1, \text{ s}$	0.0034 ± 0.00004	0.0038 ± 0.0001
#2	GDL	w_2	0.060 ± 0.008	0.07 ± 0.03
		$k_2, \text{ s}$	0.35 ± 0.08	1.4 ± 0.8
		$D_{eff,GDL}, \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$	1.3 ± 0.4	0.3 ± 0.2
		$R_{mt,GDL}, \text{ s cm}^{-1}$	16 ± 5	65 ± 43
#3	MPL	w_3	0.103 ± 0.008	0.14 ± 0.03
		$k_3, \text{ s}$	4.7 ± 0.7	9 ± 3
		$D_{eff,MPL}, \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^{-5}$	1.5 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3
		$R_{mt,MPL}, \text{ s cm}^{-1}$	566 ± 80	1084 ± 360

Some decrease in k_1 reflects a decrease in the high frequency limit response by increasing the active area size. The impact on hydrogen diffusivities in the anode is reflected by a decrease in $D_{eff,GDL}$ and $D_{eff,MPL}$ which is more pronounced for the GDLS (80 %) than the MPL (50 %). These changes reflect more problematic

liquid water elimination in the large area cell. Liquid water thickness measured in *operando* p-PEMFCs with neutron radiography [41,42] shows in-plane profile on the cathode due to inhomogeneous water evaporation rate from the surface, which is more effective at the edges of the active area, in contact with the open ambient, than at the centre where the ambient space is reduced by the columnar plate (see Fig. 1S for cell scheme and Fig. 4S for water images with neutron radiography). The water profile has, therefore, a concentration peak at the centre that is more pronounced in the larger active area cell (Fig. 4S of the Supplementary Material), and is main responsible for the loss in power density (Fig. 5). New p-PEMFC designs are currently under experimentation to palliate the inhomogeneous water accumulation that critically limits cell response when increasing the active area.

Comparative analysis of CH₂S with other gas transport techniques. Different techniques and experimental conditions can be found in the literature leading to a wide range of values of transport parameters for the GDLS and the MPL of a PEMFC. For a comparative analysis with those obtained here, it is of interest to classify the methods in three general groups, *operando*, *in-situ*, and *ex-situ* methods. *Operando* methods, like EIS, oxygen limiting current, some imaging techniques, and CH₂S, provide transport parameters in a working PEMFC and allow measuring in dependency of operation parameters and cells characteristics. Non-*operando*, *in-situ* methods, like the hydrogen limiting current, improve the control of over measuring conditions, especially temperature and humidification, but results may differ from those actually working in the cell. *Ex-situ* methods are carried out under well defined environments, typically using simple geometries with no flow or an ultra-simple flow [23], that provide reproducible values of the effective diffusivities, but can differ substantially from those working in real operation.

During *operando* CH₂S measurements, a water concentration profile develops through plane in the cell [41,42], with, approximately, dry conditions at the H₂ inlet, mild water-saturation in the GDLS, and high saturation in the layers adjacent to the membrane, *i.e.* the CL and MPL. H₂ transport finds different conditions in its path, from predominantly self-diffusion at the inlet port, followed by binary H₂

– H₂O diffusion in the GDLS, and probably dissolved in water in the highly saturated MPL and CL. CH₂S can distinguish the different transport conditions provided their characteristic times fall within the acquisition frequency window. The rather undetermined situation, and some of the assumptions implicit in the theory (Eq. 3 [9]) may be softened, as occur frequently with many operando techniques, make CH₂S most useful to monitor differences in operando transport properties with operation conditions, rather than determining rigorous and absolute values of the transport parameters.

Effective diffusivities of O₂ and H₂ in binary mixtures, for different GDLS and MPLs are given in Table V and compared in Fig. 7. In some cases, values have been calculated from relative values applying Eq. 7 without account of the saturation parameter. Chan et al. [64] using the *ex-situ* Loschmidt cell obtained for oxygen diffusivities $D_{eff,GDLS} = 7 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $D_{eff,MPL} = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, in paper based GDLS and conventional MPL (22 °C, ambient conditions), respectively. For similar GDLS types, hydrogen diffusivities with *in-situ* hydrogen pump are in the range $D_{eff,GDLS} = 0.1 - 0.5 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (room temperature, atmospheric pressure) depending on anode saturation and paper type [65]. Woven carbon cloth, similar to the GDLS used here, showed $D_{eff,GDLS} = 15 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (ambient conditions) *ex-situ* oxygen diffusivity, measured with an oxygen sensor battery, [66], while *operando* oxygen diffusivities is found to be $D_{eff,GDLS} = 0.01 - 0.04 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (60 °C, 2 atm), measured by Chevalier et al. using EIS, μ CT images and modelling [48]. In the same work, the MPL diffusivities $D_{eff,MPL} = 4.93 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (25%RH, 60 °C, 100 kPa, 1.5 A cm⁻²) was obtained, while *ex-situ* value provided by Kotaka et al. [67] is $D_{eff,MPL} = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (90%RH, 80 °C, 100 kPa, 10NL min⁻¹).

Fig. 7 shows, in summary, that GDLS diffusivities fall in the range 0.01 – 0.5 cm² s⁻¹ and MPL diffusivities are 0.005 – 0.05 cm² s⁻¹, with *ex-situ* techniques giving higher values than *in-situ* and *operando*, and dependent on porous material and experimental conditions (temperature, pressure, RH). In comparison, GDLS diffusivities with CH₂S show lower values that must be attributed to the *operando* water contents of this layer. Larger differences are observed in MPL diffusivities comparing with *in-situ* and *ex-situ* techniques. Low *operando* MPL diffusivity in

both p- and c-PEMFC reflects a high water saturation of this layer during power production, which is in consonance with other *operando* techniques showing water accumulation in this layer before moving to the GDLS [38]. In fact, CH2S values of diffusivities of $0.86 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and $1.1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ for p- and c-PEMFC are close to hydrogen diffusivities in water ($4.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ – $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$), which indicates close to 100% MPL *operando* saturation.

Table V. Effective diffusivities of GDLSs and MPLs measured with different techniques.

GDLS type	Binary gas mixture	$D_{eff,GDL}, \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	Experimental conditions	Method	Ref.
Paper based: Toray-TGP-H-120, SGL Sigracet 10 series, and Freudenberg H2315	H ₂ - Ar	0.1 – 0.5	room temperature, atmospheric pressure, dry or partially saturated	Hydrogen pump	[65]
Paper based: Toray (TGP-H-120 and TGP-H-060), SolviCore (Type A) and SGL Sigracet (10- and 25-series)	O ₂ – N ₂	$7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Ambient conditions	Loschmidt cell	[64]
Paper based Toray TGP-H-060, 5wt% PTFE	O ₂ – N ₂ (air) (50, 75, 100% RH)	$1 - 4 \cdot 10^{-2}$	25%RH, 60 °C, 2 atm, 1.5 A cm ⁻²	EIS <i>operando</i>	[48]
Paper based Toray TGP H-060, 090, 120	0.1-1.0% O ₂ – N ₂	$7.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$	90%RH, 80 °C, 10 NL min ⁻¹	Oxygen limiting current	[67]
Woven carbon cloth	O ₂ – N ₂ (air) dry	$15 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Dry ambient conditions	Oxygen battery sensor	[66]
Woven carbon cloth with 5 wt% PTFE	H ₂ – H ₂ O	$(2.4 \pm 1) \cdot 10^{-2}$	(convective) c-PEMFC. Cell current $i = 100 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, cell temperature 30 °C. Atmospheric pressure	CH2S	This work
Woven carbon cloth with 5 wt% PTFE	H ₂ – H ₂ O	$(0.036 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-2}$	(passive) p-PEMFC. Cell current $i = 100 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, cell temperature 30 °C. Atmospheric pressure	CH2S	This work
MPL type	Species	$D_{eff,MPL}, \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	Experimental conditions	Method	Reference
Commercial coating, SolviCore (Type A), 66.4 μm thickness	O ₂ – N ₂	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$	Ambient conditions	Loschmidt cell	[64]
In-house carbon black and PTFE	O ₂ – N ₂ (air) (50, 75, 100% RH)	$4.93 \cdot 10^{-3}$	25%RH, 60 °C, 100 kPa, 1.5 A cm ⁻²	EIS <i>operando</i>	[48]

Paper based Toray TGP H-060, 090, 120	0.1-1.0% O ₂ – N ₂	3.1 10 ⁻²	90%RH, 80 °C, 10 NL min ⁻¹	Ex-situ, diffusion cell	[67]
Commercial coating, 83 μm thickness	H ₂ – H ₂ O	(1.1±1.1) 10 ⁻⁵	c-PEMFC. Cell current i = 100 mA cm ⁻² , cell temperature 30 °C. Atmospheric pressure	CH2S	This work
Commercial coating, 83 μm thickness	H ₂ – H ₂ O	(0.86±0.3) 10 ⁻⁵	p-PEMFC. Cell current i = 100 mA cm ⁻² , cell temperature 30 °C. Atmospheric pressure	CH2S	This work

Fig. 7. Comparing GDLS and MPL diffusivities, for H₂ and O₂ gases. Materials, conditions, and methods indicated. Data from Table V.

4.- Conclusions

The Current-modulated Hydrogen flow-rate Spectroscopy (CH2S) has been used to study *operando* transport properties of hydrogen in the anode of a p-PEMFC, and compared with a c-PEMFC. The effects of current density and active area size on the effective hydrogen diffusivities of the GDLS and the MPL have been analyzed.

Current densities up to 180 mA cm^{-2} do not change hydrogen diffusivity in the GDLS, while it increases significantly in the MPL. The latter is explained by drier conditions in the anode caused the electroosmotic dragging of water, and higher temperature [9]. Increasing the active area size of the p-PEMFC increases transport losses, due to water accumulation at the center of the cell, where passive forces (evaporation) are less effective. Current work is concentrated in favoring the action of passive forces in larger active areas p-PEMFCs.

Lower GDLS diffusivity in p-PEMFC than in c-PEMFC reflects the slow elimination of water by natural forces. However, MPL diffusivities are low in both cell types, p- and c-PEMFC, and compared with values reported in the literature obtained with other methods, which reflects *operando* MPL water saturation close to 100%.

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